

THE ROLE OF PHRASEOLOGY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPEECH OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN SCHOOL WITH KARAKALPAK LANGUAGE OF INSTRUCTION

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the role and importance of phraseology in the development and enrichment of speech in primary school students. The influence and special role of phraseology in increasing the clarity and effectiveness of speech was also analyzed because the speech of primary school students was narrow.

Phraseologisms are one of the most common stable compounds in both oral language and fiction. Phraseologisms are an integral part of the creation of language and beautiful speech, the most vivid, distinctive, unusual, culturally significant and nationally specific, not only the characteristics of a particular language, but also the attitude of the speaker, is able to express thinking, mentality, national characteristics. Phraseologisms are stable compounds in the figurative sense that have a semantic integrity and consist of a stable relationship of two or more words before the speech process, ready to be introduced into the speech.

Phraseology is the study of fixed sets of words or “phrases.” Generally, efforts in phraseology are related to explaining the meanings and histories of these sets of words. Linguists use this kind

of research to know more about how speakers of a given language communicate to each other through multi-word sets, often called “lexical sets” or “lexical units.” Generally speaking, phraseology developed in the 20th-century. This discipline helps academics and others to get a more thorough grasp of how a certain language is used. Much of the focus of phraseology involves considering the many colloquial or idiomatic elements of a language. Phraseology researchers often also focus on idioms or idiomatic language. The category of idioms in a linguistic lexicon is a large one. Idioms include shorter phrases such as phrasal verbs, and longer phrases that speakers might identify as “sayings,” phrases that have become popular over time and that the general community has assigned a definite meaning to. Evaluating sayings any given language is a large part

of advanced phrase study, and an interesting way to look at how anthropology or culture affects language and vice versa.

Phrases usually have the same meaning. Phrases are always used figuratively. Phraseology is a whole and is used in the form of a ready-made combination of words.¹ Elementary school students, on the other hand, are not scientifically informed about phraseology. They only learn about simple phrases and syntax that belong to the syntax section of grammar. Phraseologisms are used only in the development of students' speech and to help students express themselves effectively. Phraseological idioms can be found both in textbooks and in the process of teaching the mother tongue. Like other languages, Karakalpak is a language rich in phraseology. It can be found in many educational processes, in literary texts, in works, including the use of idioms in the effective expression of the image of the protagonist, in increasing the sharpness of the language of the work of art. There are many examples of this in elementary school textbooks. For example, in Exercise 376 of the 4th grade Mother Tongue textbook, in an excerpt from the work of Oserbay Khojaniyazov: "We are looking back. A car appeared in the distance. Without saying yes, he also caught up with us. The chariot pulled the horse's saddle and stopped."² It is the teacher's job to

explain to the students the meaning of the phraseology used in this example.

Phraseologisms play an important role in developing the speech of primary school students, increasing their effectiveness, and multiplying new words in speech. Proverbs, phrases, and terms are rarely used because of their limited vocabulary. Therefore, a number of things can be done to develop phrases in children's speech. For example, after explaining the meaning of the phraseology encountered in the process of studying and analyzing works of art, texts, fairy tales, poems, and explaining to the reader in a simple and straightforward language that he understands, Writing new phrases in notebooks and doing vocabulary work will help students learn and memorize quickly. The teacher then checks that the children are using new phrases in their speech and adding them to the vocabulary they use in their daily lives.³ At the same time, the teacher can give the students a lesson on phraseology. For example, in smaller classes, such as grades 1 and 2, a teacher reinforces students' knowledge by explaining the meaning of a phraseology by composing or giving an example of a phraseology. Or in older grades, and in grades 3-4, the student can reinforce his or her knowledge of phraseology by completing a series of tasks, such as finding phrases he or she encounters independently, explaining their meaning, and composing sentences using similar examples. For example, in Oybek's novel "Kutlug Kan", Mirzakarimboy was a man who licked the fat of a snake: like all rich

¹ Hamroyeva O. Collection of lectures in the native language. - Tashkent: Akademnashr, 2018. - B 93.

² Davunov E., Kundaybergenov M., Uspanova J. Mother tongue is a subject for the 4th grade of secondary schools. - Nokis: Karakalpakstan, 2017. - B 174.

³ Pirniyazova A., Pirniyazov K., Bekniyazov K. Methods of teaching the native language in primary school. - Tashkent: Sano -standard, 2018. - P. 248.

people, he was cunning, deceitful, stubborn; he preferred caution in all things, not heartlessness. ”⁴Exercises like these can have a profound effect on a student's speech. Such classes not only develop children's speech, but also increase the respect and love of the younger generation for their mother tongue, and, of course, once again make sure that the mother tongue is a powerful, rich and beautiful language. A single speech development activity can help a student achieve both scientific and educational goals.

In sum, a phraseologism is defined as the co-occurrence of a form or a lemma of a lexical item and one or more additional linguistic elements of various kinds which functions as one semantic unit in a clause or sentence and whose frequency of co-occurrence is larger than expected on the basis of chance. The role phraseology has played in linguistic theory is quite varied. On the one hand, it is varied because theoretical frameworks or approaches in linguistics differ widely in terms of the importance attached to phraseologisms.

⁴ Oybek. Blessed is the blood. - Ghafur Ghulam Publishing House of Fiction, 1969. - B 6.

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